

The Effect of CEO Turnover and Financial Distress on Earnings Management: The Moderating Role of Institutional Ownership

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to provide empirical evidence regarding the effect of CEO turnover and financial distress on earnings management, as well as to examine the moderating role of institutional ownership in these relationships. The population of this study consists of all consumer non-cyclicals companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) during the 2021–2024 period. The sampling technique employed purposive sampling, resulting in 74 companies with a total of 296 firm-year observations. The study applied the Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA) method using STATA software. The findings indicate that CEO turnover has no significant effect on earnings management. In contrast, financial distress has a positive effect on earnings management, suggesting that financial pressure encourages companies to engage more intensively in earnings management practices. Institutional ownership is found to be unable to moderate the relationship between CEO turnover and earnings management. However, institutional ownership strengthens the effect of financial distress on earnings management. This study concludes that earnings management practices are influenced by financial conditions and managerial changes, while institutional ownership plays a complex role in corporate monitoring mechanisms. Strengthening corporate governance is essential to improve the quality of financial reporting and minimize earnings management practices. Future studies are recommended to expand the research scope to different industrial sectors and extend the observation period to better capture long-term corporate dynamics.

KEYWORDS: Earnings Management, CEO Turnover, Financial Distress, Institutional Ownership.

INTRODUCTION

Financial statements serve as an essential source of information for assessing a company's financial performance and supporting economic decision-making. Among various financial indicators, earnings are considered one of the most critical measures because they reflect and predict the quality of financial reporting (Githaiga et al., 2022). However, the accrual basis of accounting provides managerial discretion in selecting accounting policies, creating opportunities for opportunistic behavior through earnings manipulation (Alzoubi, 2018). This practice, commonly referred to as earnings management, occurs when managers intentionally influence reported earnings to achieve certain objectives, potentially at the expense of shareholders and investors (Yasa & Novialy, 2012).

Earnings management remains a persistent issue in corporate reporting, including in Indonesia. Although the consumer non-cyclicals sector is generally considered relatively stable due to its provision of essential goods, several indications of earnings management have emerged. One notable case involved PT Tiga Pilar Sejahtera Food Tbk (AISA), where financial statement inflation amounting to IDR 4 trillion was detected following a management transition and financial restatement (Sugiarto & Damayanti, 2023). Similarly, PT Akasha Wira International Tbk (ADES) experienced increasing net profits despite declining sales, a pattern often associated with discretionary earnings management (Angreini & Nurhayati, 2022; Nofianti et al., 2023). Furthermore, fluctuations in the consumer non-cyclicals stock index during 2021–2024 indicate that the sector has not fully recovered from post-pandemic economic pressures (I. N. Sari & Muslimin, 2025), potentially increasing incentives for managers to maintain favorable financial performance through earnings management.

One factor frequently associated with earnings management is CEO turnover. CEOs hold strategic authority in determining company direction and financial policies, creating incentives to demonstrate superior performance, particularly during leadership transitions (Yasa & Novialy, 2012). From the perspective of agency theory, conflicts of interest between principals and agents may motivate CEOs to manipulate earnings for personal benefits such as compensation, reputation, or job security. Similarly, positive

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accounting theory suggests that managers exploit accounting flexibility to maximize economic incentives. Empirical evidence regarding the relationship between CEO turnover and earnings management, however, remains inconclusive. Several studies report a positive relationship (Ali & Zhang, 2015; N. Putri & Fadhli, 2017; Setyawan & Anggraita, 2018), while others find no significant effect due to governance mechanisms and routine leadership succession processes (Gurusinga & Kusumadewi, 2023; Wirayudah & Sudarsani, 2021; Prawestri et al., 2022).

In addition to managerial changes, financial distress may also influence earnings management behavior. Financial distress reflects deteriorating financial conditions that increase managerial pressure to maintain corporate legitimacy and avoid negative market reactions. Agency theory explains that such conditions intensify information asymmetry, encouraging managers to engage in earnings management either to attract investors, avoid debt covenant violations, or secure debt restructuring (Silva et al., 2023). Prior studies predominantly suggest that financial distress positively affects earnings management (Aljughaiman et al., 2023; Hanum et al., 2024; Nguyen et al., 2024; Winata et al., 2025). Nevertheless, several studies report insignificant relationships, indicating that some firms prioritize transparency and long-term reputation over opportunistic reporting behavior (Irawan & Apriwenni, 2021; Kristyaningsih et al., 2021; Nurulita & Utami, 2024).

Given these inconsistent findings, this study introduces institutional ownership as a moderating variable. Institutional ownership is expected to function as an external governance mechanism capable of reducing managerial opportunism through stronger monitoring (Arthur & Tumiwa, 2018). According to agency theory, institutional investors can mitigate information asymmetry and constrain opportunistic managerial actions, particularly during CEO transitions and periods of financial distress. Prior evidence suggests that stronger governance mechanisms may reduce earnings management incentives under financial pressure (Sari & Helmi, 2023).

This study contributes to the literature by examining the moderating role of institutional ownership in the relationship between CEO turnover, financial distress, and earnings management in consumer non-cyclicals companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange during 2021–2024. Additionally, firm size and profitability are incorporated as control variables to minimize external bias and improve the robustness of the findings (Kurniawati & Panggabean, 2020).

LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS

Based on agency theory, conflicts of interest between shareholders (principals) and managers (agents) may encourage CEOs to engage in opportunistic behavior to protect their positions and enhance perceived performance (Yuliana, 2011). CEO turnover creates incentives for newly appointed CEOs to adjust accounting policies in order to establish a favorable market perception and demonstrate managerial competence during the early years of tenure. From the perspective of positive accounting theory, new CEOs may exploit accounting discretion to reset performance benchmarks or improve future earnings prospects. Prior studies indicate that CEO turnover is associated with higher earnings management practices, particularly through discretionary accruals aimed at income-decreasing strategies in the early period of leadership (Choi et al., 2012; Glaum & Landsman, 2023; Adiasih & Kusuma, 2011; Godfrey et al., 2000). Empirical findings by Indirani and Priyadi (2022), Yuliana (2011), Vernando and Rakhman (2018), and Amelia and Eriandani (2021) further support the argument that newly appointed CEOs tend to manage earnings to shape performance expectations and strengthen their reputation. Therefore, the first hypothesis is formulated as follows:

H1: CEO turnover positively affects earnings management.

Agency theory explains that financial distress intensifies conflicts between managers and shareholders due to increased pressure to maintain firm performance and avoid negative consequences such as bankruptcy risks or debt covenant violations (Sari & Meiranto, 2017). Under such conditions, managers may have incentives to manipulate reported earnings to maintain investor confidence and preserve corporate legitimacy. Consistent with positive accounting theory, managers tend to select accounting procedures that maximize personal or organizational objectives, particularly during periods of financial pressure (Irawan & Apriwenni, 2021). Empirical studies generally indicate that financially distressed firms are more likely to engage in earnings management as a strategy to conceal poor financial performance and meet stakeholder expectations (Chairunnisa et al., 2021; Mellennia & Khomsiyah, 2023; Santosa et al., 2022; Setyaningrum & Nursita, 2024; Nurulita & Utami, 2024; Setiawan & Dwiana Putra, 2019). Therefore, the second hypothesis is formulated as follows:

H2: Financial distress positively affects earnings management.

Institutional ownership is considered an important corporate governance mechanism that strengthens monitoring over managerial behavior, particularly during leadership transitions. According to agency theory, institutional investors possess stronger incentives, analytical capabilities, and resources to monitor managerial decisions and reduce opportunistic behavior, including earnings manipulation (Chaironisa & Suryanti, 2024). Although CEO turnover may encourage newly appointed CEOs to

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engage in earnings management to reshape performance perceptions (Glaum & Landsman, 2023; Adiasih & Kusuma, 2011; Godfrey et al., 2000), stronger institutional ownership may constrain such practices through stricter supervision and governance pressure. Consequently, firms with higher institutional ownership are expected to reduce opportunistic earnings management following CEO turnover. Therefore, the third hypothesis is formulated as follows:

H3: Institutional ownership weakens the positive effect of CEO turnover on earnings management.

From the agency theory perspective, financial distress increases managerial incentives to manipulate earnings due to heightened pressure to maintain financial stability and avoid adverse outcomes, such as reputational damage and debt covenant violations (Chairunnisa et al., 2021; Mellennia & Khomsiyah, 2023; Santosa et al., 2022; Setyaningrum & Nursita, 2024). However, institutional ownership may function as an effective monitoring mechanism to reduce managerial opportunism (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). Institutional investors tend to enforce stronger oversight and encourage transparent financial reporting, thereby limiting aggressive accounting practices during periods of financial distress (Kusumaningtyas et al., 2019). In this context, high institutional ownership is expected to mitigate the tendency of financially distressed firms to engage in earnings management. Therefore, the fourth hypothesis is formulated as follows:

H4: Institutional ownership weakens the positive effect of financial distress on earnings management.

METHODS

This study employed a quantitative explanatory research design to examine the effect of CEO turnover and financial distress on earnings management, as well as the moderating role of institutional ownership. The population consisted of all consumer non-cyclicals companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) during the 2021–2024 period. Using purposive sampling, 74 firms were selected, resulting in 296 firm-year observations. Secondary data were obtained from annual reports and financial statements published through the IDX and company websites. Earnings management, as the dependent variable, was proxied by discretionary accruals measured using the Modified Jones Model, which is widely recognized as one of the most robust models for detecting earnings management (Indriani & Pujiono, 2021). CEO turnover was measured as a dummy variable, assigning a value of 1 for firms experiencing CEO changes and 0 otherwise, following Huson et al. (2001) and Weisbach (1988). Financial distress was measured using the modified Altman Z-Score model, consisting of working capital, retained earnings, earnings before interest and taxes, and equity-to-debt ratio components, as a predictor of financial difficulties prior to bankruptcy (Setyaningrum & Nursita, 2024). Institutional ownership, as the moderating variable, was measured by the percentage of institutional shareholdings relative to total outstanding shares (Sumanto & Asrori, 2014). Furthermore, firm size and profitability were included as control variables, measured using the natural logarithm of total assets and Return on Assets (ROA), respectively (Tannaya & Lasdi, 2021; Hapsari, 2019). The data were analyzed using Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA) with STATA software to test both the direct and moderating effects among variables.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Model Selection and Diagnostic Tests

To determine the most appropriate panel regression model, this study employed the Chow test, Hausman test, and Lagrange Multiplier (LM) test. The results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Model Selection Test Results

Test Type	Model Comparison	Result	Decision
Chow Test	CEM vs FEM	0.0000	FEM
Hausman Test	FEM vs REM	0.0000	FEM
Lagrange Multiplier Test	CEM vs REM	0.0000	REM

Primary Data, 2026

The Chow test result indicates a probability value of 0.0000 (< 0.05), suggesting that the Fixed Effect Model (FEM) is more appropriate than the Common Effect Model (CEM). Similarly, the Hausman test produced a probability value of 0.0000 (< 0.05), indicating that FEM is preferable to the Random Effect Model (REM). Although the LM test suggested REM, the consistency of both Chow and Hausman tests supports the use of the Fixed Effect Model (FEM) as the most appropriate estimation model for this study.

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Furthermore, classical assumption tests confirmed the adequacy of the regression model. The normality test using skewness-kurtosis and Shapiro-Wilk tests showed probability values of 0.0526 and 0.08982, respectively, exceeding the 5% significance threshold, indicating normally distributed residuals. Multicollinearity was not identified, as all Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values remained below 10, ranging from 1.04 to 2.17. The heteroscedasticity test also indicated homoscedastic residuals ($\text{Prob} > \chi^2 = 0.9999$), while the Wooldridge test confirmed the absence of autocorrelation ($\text{Prob} > F = 0.0961$). These findings suggest that the regression model satisfies the required assumptions and is suitable for further hypothesis testing.

Moderated Regression Analysis Results

The Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA) results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Moderated Regression Analysis Results

Variables	Coefficient	Standard Error	P-value	Decision
CEOCHG	-0.002	0.004	0.569	Rejected
FD	0.004	0.000	0.000	Supported
INST	0.003	0.004	0.549	-
CEOCHG × INST	0.005	0.004	0.213	Rejected
FD × INST	0.001	0.000	0.032	Rejected
SIZE	-0.014	0.001	0.000	-
ROA	-0.077	0.003	0.000	-
Constant	0.435	0.017	0.000	-

Primary Data, 2026

The regression model produced an adjusted R^2 value of 0.967, indicating that 96.7% of the variation in earnings management can be explained by CEO turnover, financial distress, institutional ownership, firm size, profitability, and the moderating interactions included in the model. Meanwhile, the remaining 3.3% may be explained by factors outside the model. In addition, the F-test showed a probability value of 0.000, confirming that the independent variables collectively explain earnings management and that the model is statistically robust.

Hypothesis Testing and Discussion

CEO Turnover and Earnings Management

The results indicate that CEO turnover has no significant effect on earnings management ($\beta = -0.002$, $p = 0.569$), leading to the rejection of H1. This finding suggests that changes in top leadership do not necessarily encourage managers to engage in opportunistic financial reporting practices within consumer non-cyclicals firms. A possible explanation is that CEO succession in many firms is conducted as part of routine governance processes, such as retirement, succession planning, or the completion of managerial tenure, rather than as a response to financial pressure or poor performance.

From a corporate governance perspective, CEO turnover may not weaken monitoring mechanisms because former CEOs often remain involved in supervisory roles, such as board commissioners, thereby maintaining oversight over managerial decisions (Adiasih & Kusuma, 2012). Effective board monitoring may reduce managerial discretion and discourage earnings manipulation during transition periods. This result is consistent with studies by Gurusinga and Kusumadewi (2023), Wirayudah and Sudarsani (2021), Prawestri et al. (2022), Bouaziz et al. (2020), and Suhartati et al. (2024), which found no significant relationship between CEO turnover and earnings management. However, this finding contradicts Ali and Zhang (2015), N. Putri and Fadhliha (2017), and Setyawan and Anggraita (2018), who documented that newly appointed CEOs tend to manipulate earnings to shape favorable market perceptions during their early tenure.

The finding also challenges agency theory and positive accounting theory, which predict that managerial transitions may intensify information asymmetry and incentivize opportunistic accounting choices. In this context, CEO turnover appears insufficient to trigger earnings management, suggesting that other firm-specific governance mechanisms may play a more dominant role.

Financial Distress and Earnings Management

The results demonstrate that financial distress positively and significantly affects earnings management ($\beta = 0.004$, $p = 0.000$), supporting H2. This finding implies that firms experiencing greater financial pressure are more likely to engage in earnings management practices. Financially distressed firms may attempt to present a more favorable financial condition by accelerating revenue recognition, delaying expenses, or adjusting accrual policies to maintain investor confidence and avoid negative market reactions.

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This result is consistent with agency theory, which explains that financial distress intensifies conflicts of interest between principals and agents due to increased managerial pressure to maintain corporate legitimacy and avoid reputational damage. Under such conditions, managers may pursue opportunistic reporting strategies to preserve their positions and reassure stakeholders regarding firm performance. Similarly, positive accounting theory explains that managers tend to select accounting methods that maximize economic benefits under adverse financial conditions.

The finding supports prior studies by Aljughaiman et al. (2023), Winata et al. (2025), Hanum et al. (2024), Nguyen et al. (2024), Chairunnisa et al. (2021), Mellennia and Khomsiyah (2023), Santosa et al. (2022), and Setyaningrum and Nursita (2024), which concluded that financial distress increases firms' tendency to manipulate earnings. However, the result contradicts Irawan and Apriwenni (2021), Kristyaningsih et al. (2021), Nurulita and Utami (2024), and Tannaya and Lasdi (2021), who found no significant relationship. This discrepancy may be explained by differences in industrial characteristics, governance quality, and managerial incentives across research contexts.

The Moderating Role of Institutional Ownership in the Relationship Between CEO Turnover and Earnings Management

The interaction between CEO turnover and institutional ownership was found to be statistically insignificant ($\beta = 0.005, p = 0.213$), resulting in the rejection of H3. This finding indicates that institutional ownership is unable to moderate the relationship between CEO turnover and earnings management. In other words, institutional investors do not appear to strengthen or weaken managerial incentives to manipulate earnings following leadership changes.

One possible explanation is that CEO turnover is not always perceived by institutional investors as a high-risk event associated with financial reporting manipulation. In many cases, CEO succession occurs as part of routine organizational restructuring or succession planning rather than as an indicator of declining performance (Prawestri et al., 2022). Consequently, institutional investors may not intensify their monitoring activities during leadership transitions.

This finding aligns with studies by Subhan (2011), Agustia (2013), and Angel et al. (2025), which suggest that institutional ownership does not always function effectively as a governance mechanism to reduce earnings management. Institutional investors may prioritize investment returns over active monitoring, thereby limiting their effectiveness in constraining managerial opportunism. Accordingly, the result does not fully support agency theory, which assumes that institutional ownership should reduce agency conflicts and strengthen monitoring over managerial behavior.

The Moderating Role of Institutional Ownership in the Relationship Between Financial Distress and Earnings Management

Contrary to the proposed hypothesis, the interaction between financial distress and institutional ownership was found to positively and significantly affect earnings management ($\beta = 0.001, p = 0.032$). Thus, H4 is rejected, indicating that institutional ownership strengthens rather than weakens the positive relationship between financial distress and earnings management.

This finding suggests that institutional ownership may not always function as an effective monitoring mechanism during periods of financial pressure. Instead, institutional investors may share managerial incentives to maintain firm profitability and stock price stability, indirectly encouraging more optimistic financial reporting during periods of financial distress. In this context, institutional investors may prioritize short-term financial performance over transparent reporting, thereby reinforcing managerial incentives to engage in earnings management.

The result is consistent with Ikram S et al. (2024), which found that institutional ownership does not necessarily reduce earnings management under financial distress conditions. Furthermore, Maryanti and Nursiana (2025) argued that institutional investors may, in certain contexts, encourage managers to present more favorable earnings information to maintain market confidence. This finding also resonates with Porter's (1992) argument that institutional investors often prioritize short-term financial outcomes, potentially weakening their monitoring effectiveness.

From an agency theory perspective, this finding highlights that institutional ownership does not universally reduce agency problems. Instead, monitoring effectiveness may depend on investor incentives and the contextual pressures faced by firms. Therefore, institutional ownership should not automatically be assumed to function as a strong governance mechanism capable of mitigating opportunistic managerial behavior.

CONCLUSION

This study examined the effect of CEO turnover and financial distress on earnings management, as well as the moderating role of institutional ownership among consumer non-cyclicals companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange during the 2021–2024 period. The findings reveal that CEO turnover does not significantly affect earnings management, indicating that changes in top leadership do not necessarily encourage opportunistic financial reporting practices. In contrast, financial distress has a positive and significant effect on earnings management, suggesting that firms experiencing financial pressure are more likely to engage in

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earnings manipulation to maintain financial stability and stakeholder confidence. Furthermore, institutional ownership is found to be unable to moderate the relationship between CEO turnover and earnings management, indicating limited monitoring effectiveness during leadership transitions. However, contrary to the proposed hypothesis, institutional ownership strengthens the positive relationship between financial distress and earnings management, implying that institutional investors may prioritize short-term financial performance and firm stability during periods of financial pressure, thereby indirectly reinforcing managerial incentives for earnings management.

Managerial Implications

This study provides theoretical implications by extending agency theory and positive accounting theory in explaining earnings management behavior under financial pressure and managerial transition. The findings suggest that financial distress remains a strong driver of opportunistic reporting behavior, while institutional ownership does not always function as an effective governance mechanism and may, under certain circumstances, reinforce earnings management incentives. Practically, the results highlight the importance for regulators and corporate stakeholders to strengthen governance and monitoring mechanisms, particularly in financially distressed firms, while encouraging institutional investors to adopt more active and transparent oversight practices to improve the quality of financial reporting and reduce opportunistic managerial behavior.

REFERENCES

- 1) Adiasih, P., & Kusuma, I. W. (2011). Manajemen laba pada saat pergantian CEO (Dirut) di Indonesia. *Jurnal Akuntansi dan Keuangan*, 13(2), 67–79.
- 2) Aljughaiman, A. A., Huy, T., Quang, V., & Du, A. (2023). The Covid-19 outbreak, corporate financial distress and earnings management. *International Review of Financial Analysis*, 88, 102675. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.irfa.2023.102675>
- 3) Alzoubi, E. S. S. (2018). Audit quality, debt financing, and earnings management: Evidence from Jordan. *Journal of International Accounting, Auditing and Taxation*, 30, 69–84. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intaccudtax.2017.12.001>
- 4) Amelia, & Eriandani, R. (2021). CEO characteristics and earnings management: Evidence from Indonesia. *Journal of Management and Business*, 20(2), 141–154.
- 5) Angel, Suharti, Anton, A., Yusrizal, & Siringoringo, S. E. (2025). The effect of institutional ownership, leverage and profitability on earnings management. *Jurnal Bisnis Terapan*, 5(2), 142–155.
- 6) Arthur, R., & Tumiwa, F. (2018). Institutional ownership and earnings management. *International Journal of Applied Business & International Management*, 3(1).
- 7) Bouaziz, D., Salhi, B., & Jarboui, A. (2020). CEO characteristics and earnings management: Empirical evidence from France. *Journal of Financial Reporting and Accounting*, 18(1), 77–110. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JFRA-01-2019-0008>
- 8) Chaironisa, Z., & Suryanti, H. (2024). The moderating role institutional ownership and tax planning in earning management. *[Journal Name]*, 9(1), 226–239.
- 9) Chairunnisa, Z., Rasmini, M., & Alexandri, M. B. (2021). Pengaruh financial distress terhadap manajemen laba pada perusahaan sub sektor telekomunikasi. *Inovasi*, 17(3), 387–394.
- 10) Choi, J.-S., Kwak, Y.-M., & Choe, C. (2012). Earnings management surrounding CEO turnover: Evidence from Korea.
- 11) Dwijayanti, P. F., & Wijaya, H. (2024). CEO turnover and earnings management: Can board gender diversity restraining earnings management? *9(2)*, 189–198.
- 12) Githaiga, P. N., Kabete, P. M., & Bonareri, T. C. (2022). Board characteristics and earnings management: Does firm size matter? *Cogent Business & Management*, 9(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2022.2088573>
- 13) Glaum, M., & Landsman, W. (2023). Earnings management and newly appointed CEOs.
- 14) Godfrey, J., Mather, P., Ramsay, A., Jones, M., & Peirson, G. (2000). Earnings and impression management in financial reports: The case of CEO changes.
- 15) Gujarati, D. N., & Porter, D. C. (2009). *Basic econometrics* (5th ed.). McGraw-Hill.
- 16) Gurusina, S. K., & Kusumadewi, N. L. G. L. (2023). Pengaruh leverage, ukuran perusahaan, dan pergantian CEO terhadap manajemen laba perusahaan perbankan. *Prosiding Working Papers Series in Management*, 15(1), 201–221. <https://doi.org/10.25170/wpm.v15i1.4660>
- 17) Hanum, N., Wardhani, D. K., & Utami, R. A. B. (2024). The effect of financial distress and profitability on earning management. *2(2)*, 26–35.
- 18) Ikram S, M., Gaffar, A. N., Arzalsyah, Imam, M. A., Syahrani, D., & Purniawan, D. (2024). Kepemilikan institusional dalam memoderasi praktik manajemen laba di Indonesia. *Edunomika*, 8(3), 1–20.
- 19) Indirani, P., & Priyadi, M. P. (2022). Pengaruh beban pajak tangguhan, beban pajak kini, perencanaan pajak dan pergantian CEO terhadap manajemen laba. *11(2)*, 1689–1699.

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- 20) Indriani, A. D., & Pujiono, P. (2021). Analysis of earnings management practices using the modified Jones model. *11*(1), 235–243. <https://doi.org/10.14414/tiar.v11i2.2383>
- 21) Irawan, S., & Apriwenni, P. (2021). Pengaruh free cash flow, financial distress, dan investment opportunity set terhadap manajemen laba. *Jurnal Akuntansi Bisnis*, *14*(1), 24–37. <https://doi.org/10.30813/jab.v14i1.2458>
- 22) Jensen, M. C., & Meckling, W. H. (1976). Theory of the firm: Managerial behavior, agency cost and ownership structure. *Journal of Financial Economics*, *3*, 305–360.
- 23) Kristyaningsih, P., Hariyani, D. S., & Sudrajat, M. A. (2021). Financial distress terhadap manajemen laba. *Business Innovation and Entrepreneurship Journal*, *3*(3), 151–156.
- 24) Kurniawati, A., & Panggabean, R. R. (2020). Firm size, financial distress, audit quality, and earnings management of banking companies. *436*, 413–417. <https://doi.org/10.2991/assehr.k.200529.086>
- 25) Maryanti, E., & Nursiana, A. (2025). Pengaruh financial distress dan leverage terhadap konservatisme akuntansi dengan kepemilikan institusional sebagai variabel moderasi. *Jurnal Akuntansi*, *19*(1), 27–39.
- 26) Mellennia, D. A., & Khomsiyah. (2023). Financial distress terhadap praktik manajemen laba dan good corporate governance sebagai variabel moderasi di masa pandemi Covid-19. *Jurnal Informasi, Perpajakan, Akuntansi, dan Keuangan Publik*, *18*(1), 69–86. <https://doi.org/10.25105/jipak.v18i1.15768>
- 27) Nguyen, Q., Kim, M. H., & Ali, S. (2024). Corporate governance and earnings management: Evidence from Vietnamese listed firms. *International Review of Economics and Finance*, *89*, 775–801. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iref.2023.07.084>
- 28) Nurulita, S., & Utami, T. (2024). Pengaruh perencanaan pajak, beban pajak tangguhan, dan financial distress terhadap manajemen laba. *AKUA: Jurnal Akuntansi dan Keuangan*, *3*(1), 1–11.
- 29) Prawestri, A. D., Iriyanto, B. S., & Putri, N. K. (2022). Pengaruh pergantian CEO dan pengungkapan CSR terhadap manajemen laba. *JIEF: Journal of Islamic Economics and Finance*, *2*(1), 43–65.
- 30) Putri, N., & Fadhlia, W. (2017). Pergantian CEO dan manajemen laba pada perusahaan manufaktur Indonesia. *Jurnal Ilmiah Mahasiswa Ekonomi Akuntansi*, *2*(3).
- 31) Santosa, C., Amiruddin, A., & Rasyid, S. (2022). Pengaruh asimetri informasi, financial distress, dan komite audit terhadap manajemen laba. *Akrual: Jurnal Bisnis dan Akuntansi Kontemporer*, *15*(1), 12–22.
- 32) Sari, I. N., & Muslimin. (2025). Determinants of earnings management in Indonesian consumer non-cyclical companies. *Bima Journal – Business Management and Accounting*, *6*(2), 1273–1284.
- 33) Sari, T., & Helmi. (2023). Pengaruh financial distress terhadap praktik manajemen laba dengan kepemilikan institusional. *Jurnal Ekonomi Trisakti*, *3*(2), 3479–3488.
- 34) Setiawan, P. E., & Dwiana Putra, I. M. P. (2019). Keputusan pemilihan strategi manajemen laba pada perusahaan yang mengalami financial distress di Indonesia. *Jurnal Ilmiah Akuntansi dan Bisnis*, *14*(2), 196.
- 35) Setyaningrum, I., & Nursita, M. (2024). Pengaruh pertumbuhan perusahaan, umur perusahaan dan financial distress terhadap manajemen laba. *Akademik: Jurnal Mahasiswa Ekonomi & Bisnis*, *4*(3), 1216–1229.
- 36) Setyawan, M. B., & Anggraita, V. (2018). The effects of CEO tenure on earnings management. *Advances in Economics, Business and Management Research*, *55*, 104–111.
- 37) Silva, R., Tardin, N., Monte-Mor, D., Ferreira, T., & Jeldes, F. (2023). Big bath accounting in an emerging market: Evidence from newly appointed CEOs in Brazil. *18*(1), 93–103.
- 38) Sumanto, B., & Asrori, K. (2014). Pengaruh kepemilikan institusional terhadap manajemen laba. *3*(1), 44–52.
- 39) Suhartati, M., Rizki, W., & Putri, E. (2024). Analysis of the effect of CEO change and financial distress on earnings management. *4*(3), 299–305.
- 40) Tannaya, C. I. N., & Lasdi, L. (2021). Pengaruh financial distress terhadap manajemen laba dengan good corporate governance sebagai variabel moderasi. *Jurnal Ilmiah Mahasiswa Akuntansi*, *10*(1), 31–40.
- 41) Vernando, A., & Rakhman, F. (2018). Masa kerja CEO dan manajemen laba. *Jurnal Akuntansi dan Keuangan Indonesia*, *15*(2), 202–216.
- 42) Wirayudah, & Sudarsani. (2021). [Reference incomplete in original list].
- 43) Yasa, G. W., & Novialy, Y. (2012). Indikasi manajemen laba oleh chief executive officer (CEO) baru pada perusahaan-perusahaan yang terdaftar di pasar modal Indonesia. *Jurnal Ilmiah Akuntansi dan Bisnis*, *1–24*.
- 44) Yuliana, C. (2011). Pengaruh leverage, pergantian CEO dan motivasi pajak terhadap manajemen laba. *Jurnal Riset Akuntansi dan Keuangan*, *7*(1), 19.